

Let's care

BUILDING SAFE AND CARING SCHOOLS
TO FOSTER EDUCATIONAL INCLUSION
AND SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENT

D6.3 First Dissemination and Communication Report

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Executive summary

The first dissemination and communication report presents and analyses the activities implemented by the consortium to promote LET'S CARE objectives and approach to the main target groups during the first year of the project. This report analyses different levels of engagement of target groups considering the quantitative impact, the geographical level addressed, and the kind of activities implemented.

In total, there have been a total of 157 communication and dissemination activities.

The **communication** activities have registered:

- 1.500 visitors to the project's website.
- 69.136 views to the media articles related to the project.
- 85.768 people reached by mailing lists.
- 3.448 persons reached through the social media.
- 2.927 participants to conferences.
- 247 persons involved in information meetings.
- 1.364 participants to other events.

The **dissemination** activities have involved a total of 4.302 participants in training events.

The document presents the results of the quantitative data collection in 4 chapters. The introduction describes the methodology and the levels of engagement considered. Then there are 2 chapters about the results of the communication and dissemination activities, presented with graphics and detailed tables. The last chapter draws conclusions from the data collected and proposes a forecast for future activities.

1. Introduction

The first phase of communication and dissemination has focused on raising awareness among the target groups (especially teachers and principals) about the project's values and the pillars of LET'S CARE. The **communication** activities made it possible to spread awareness about the project's potential to change the world of education, starting from the real needs and participation of those who experience it daily (teachers, managers, families, and students). Through the training courses linked to the project's founding values, "seeds" have been metaphorically planted to lead to the active participation of teachers and other stakeholders in the Community of Schools (T1.2), the LET'S CARE Network (T1.3) and the continuation of the process of change beyond the end of the project. The **dissemination** phase started with training courses held by experts to help teachers increase their awareness of how their way of experiencing school and teaching can contribute to students' well-being. The courses provided participants with educational methodologies and strategies conceptually linked to the project approach and essential references to social and pedagogical theories. These dissemination moments have been an important food for thought for everyone about the role of the teachers and how much influence their actions have on learners' well-being and on shaping the future of our societies. The result of these activities has been a very strong interest and motivation among teachers to participate in developing the project through the Community of Schools.

This first dissemination and communication report of the LET'S CARE project is based on the activities undertaken by the consortium **from October 2022 (M1) to August 2023 (M11)**¹. This analysis covers qualitative and quantitative perspectives by considering the type of activities, the geographical impact, and the number of persons reached or involved.

An initial Gantt diagram, reported in D6.2 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, has been developed, identifying the main deadline and working periods for communication and dissemination activities. The plan is to guide the partners and allowing to monitor and plan the activities. Each partner has been responsible for implementing communication and dissemination activities and report them on a shared spreadsheet², collecting the primary information necessary for the impact analysis, such as the type of activity, the date and description of the activity developed, the venue, the geographical level, the dissemination context, the number of people reached or involved for each target group and any links to demonstrate the implementation

¹ Since the document had to be submitted on M12 it has not been possible to collect and analyse the data of September 2023. The activities implemented during this month will be included in the D6.4.

² The reporting table of the first year of the project is available at this link:
<https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/s/YNs2ckWgLzcfGTL>

1.1 Communication materials

As a base for the communication processes, the visual identity of the project has been developed by creating the logo and defining the project's colours and set of fonts to be used (M1). The visual identity has been integrated into the D6.1 Project's website (M3).

A second step in defining internal visual identity has been the development of templates for presentations, deliverables, and attendance sheets, which have been shared with the consortium (M3).

The material to facilitate the communication with the target groups has been produced through M7 to M12 and included:

- 2 leaflets: one about the [project](#) addressed to the general public and one about the [research model](#) addressed to the public interested in the technical details of the project implementation (such as researchers and project managers);
- 1 [roll-up](#) for the general project communication at face-to-face public events,
- 1 general model [project presentation](#) for schools addressed to principals, headteachers and teachers,
- 1 newsletter,
- 1 [press release](#) that the partners can use to present the project to the media,
- 1 [promotional video](#) developed by a teacher to present the project to their peers (published on the homepage of the [LET'S CARE Hub](#))

To support the consortium in implementing effective communication, POLO has also developed a [Stakeholder Involvement Strategy](#) document.

In Annex 1, it is possible to find examples of the graphic materials and direct links to download them. The material has been produced using the Canva online service so the partners can easily translate and adapt it to their dissemination context.

1.2 Process of co-creation of the communication material

In order to ensure the co-creation process, from the very beginning of the project, POLO set up a team of teachers who worked out the strategies and provided input to attract other colleagues. Teachers communicated their needs and helped to develop simplified presentations to make the project easily understandable and usable by interested colleagues.

The creation of some of the communication materials have seen the active involvement of target group representatives:

- A teacher produced [the first project video](#), designed specifically for their peers.
- The presentation to introduce the project to the schools has been refined with input from a school director, a headteacher, and teachers to use more effective and clear language.
- The research model leaflet has been developed based on Comillas' ideas to appeal to a technically skilled audience. Communication activities and dissemination events have facilitated target groups' direct involvement, enhancing educational environments. The initial communication activities have helped gather and analyse needs, leading to tailored dissemination activities like training courses that have provided teachers with safe teaching strategies.

2. Results of the communication activities

2.1 Awareness

The awareness level aims to keep the general audience informed and aware of the project's main topics and activities. This level involves the recipients more passively, and, in most cases, it is impossible to identify the degree of participation and the interest of the addressees. This level is crucial to involve the target groups in the following stages of participation.

The communication activities implemented by the consortium have reached a considerable number of recipients. The partners have published articles and conveyed information about the project through different media at the local and national levels.

The main communication contexts considered in this quantitative analysis are:

- Online communication:
 - LET'S CARE website;
 - Partner's media articles about the project's aims and activities
 - Partners' social media;
 - Mailing lists, newsletters.
- Potential views on:
 - Online newspapers;
 - Website homepages or general articles.

The main contents communicated through these media are:

- Information about the project, objectives and description;
- Events related to the project;
- Aims of the project;
- Contents of the project;
- Activities undertaken and future activities.

2.1.1 LET'S CARE website

LET'S CARE website (www.letscaresproject.eu) serves as a gateway to showcase the project, detailing its outcomes and ongoing activities. It is the primary interface for engaging with the project's audience, offering an initial insight into its scope and objectives. IPA has developed the platform in close collaboration with the partners, ensuring the co-creation process. It has been launched on M3. The website has been strategically updated in M10 to reflect the project's progress, thereby maintaining a view of achievements and dynamics.

The website analytics (using the GDPR-compliant service Fathom Analytics) have registered:

- 1.500 visitors.
- 3.900 views.
- 1:34 average time spent on the website.
- 70% bounce rate.

The main visitors are from Italy, Spain, Portugal, and Austria.

Image 1 – Web analytics from Fathom Analytics: Visitors, Views, time, bounce rate

Image 2 – Web analytics from Fathom Analytics: other data

2.1.2 Potential readers

POLO has decided to include references to the project on web pages with a usual high number of visitors, to spread awareness about the project's existence and invite the visitors (usually teachers) to get to know more about it. The total number of views of these pages (i.e. website homepage <https://www.europole.org/>, training courses <https://www.europole.org/formazione-2022-2023/>, projects' list <https://www.europole.org/sommario-progetti-della-rete/>) is over 8 million.

Furthermore, POLO has widely presented the project during the international conference "Peace as educational value – A school without conflicts", held in Verona in November 2022. The communication media about this event has reached more than 35.000 visitors to the conference presentation page (<https://www.europole.org/conference2022> and <https://www.europole.org/conferenza2022>) and almost 3 million potential readers through the communication campaign in newspapers: information about the conference have been shared through newspapers and webpages at local (such as L'Arena, VeronaNews...), regional (such as RaiNews Veneto...), national (such as Virgilio, Libero...) and European (such as Agenparl.eu) level. Identifying the exact number of people reached by these communication activities has not been possible since these data are not public or available. The number of followers and the media kits provided have been taken into account to calculate this number.

2.1.3 Online communication

The partners have been committed to spreading information about the project to the general public by posting articles on their websites or social media. Partners have presented LET'S CARE in specific posts or have included information and links about the project in articles presenting related activities. In Spain, an article about the project was published in the local printed newspaper "La Gaceta Extremeña de la Educación". In quantitative terms, this means of communication has reached a high number of target groups who are now aware of the project's existence, even if not all of the viewers have required more information about the project.

Another successful means of communication has been mailing lists to send information about the project's contents, activities, opportunities, etc., especially to teachers. The partners have used their internal databases to share that information and reported the total number of individuals reached. This mean is more targeted and addressed to specific stakeholders. This way, the partners have shared more detailed information about the project.

The number of people reached by each type of communication is as follows:

- Media articles: 69.163

- Social media: 3448
- Promotional videos: 9
- Mailing lists: 85.768

The list of the links to the web pages, media articles and posts on social networks can be found in Annex 2.

A table with the detailed numbers per each partner can be found in Annex 3 (table 1).

2.2 Information

Information aims to raise interest among the target groups and provide direct access to the project contents. The information events have been an opportunity to broaden the network of stakeholders and improve the understanding of LET'S CARE aims and contents, thus contributing to achieving the project's objectives. The participants in the different information events have shown interest in the project and its contents.

The analysis of the data collected from the participation in the information events has considered:

- Contexts of implementation of the activity (Conferences, Information Meetings, Events, Clustering Activities).
- Target groups (Students, Students' Families, Education Scientific Community, Teachers, Schools, Policy Makers & Authorities, European Policy Makers, NGOs & Advocacy Organisations, General Public, Others).
- Geographical level (Local, Regional, National, European, International).

2.2.1 Contexts of implementation

The partners have been committed to promoting the project in order to involve the target groups, provide them with more information, and share the contents of the project. This second step of communication has a stronger impact in terms of knowledge and engagement to the project's activities.

In total, communication events organised by the consortium were:

- 10 conferences attended by 2.927 people
- 11 information meetings with the participation of 247 stakeholders
- 6 events with 1.340 people

- 1 clustering activity which have involved 24 people.

Detailed tables per partner can be found in Annex 4 (tables 2 and 3).

The general impact of these information activities has been good, with a total of 4538 persons reached. Partners have organised or participated in different events, presenting the project and its objectives to recruit more participants to the Community of Schools or the Network of Stakeholders. The information meetings reached a good number of participants and paved the way for the direct implementation of the project's activities.

LET'S CARE has been presented during 5 conferences organised or attended by COMILLAS with a total of 2157 persons. Other conferences have been organised in Poland (2 conferences and 520 people reached), in Italy (170 people reached) and in Portugal (65 people reached). FHV has submitted and presented a paper titled "*Design and development of a Service System for fostering student's attachment security: a Content Management System based Approach*" at the 2023 ICE/IEEE conference. The paper will be published on their website within the next few months. More detailed description of the participation in conferences are reported in Annex 5.

COM has also participated in a clustering event in Ljubljana (Slovenia), "Research data management when working with children and youth", on the 27th and 28th of March 2023. A member of the Comillas team was invited to participate by the COORDINATE H2020 Project and received a scholarship to attend. The collaboration with this project can further develop a network of scholars studying Child Well-Being in Europe and promote knowledge exchange.

2.2.2 Target groups

The consortium has involved the widest possible audience in the information events and activities in order to motivate them to become an active part of the LET'S CARE network and the Community of Schools.

The audience involved consists of the following target groups:

- 587 students
- 83 students' families
- 205 education scientific communities
- 908 teachers
- 2.236 schools
- 155 policy makers and authorities
- 5 European policy makers

- 27 NGOs and advocacy organisations
- 330 general public
- 2 Others

A detailed table per partner can be found in Annex 4 (table 4).

As the data clearly show, the partners mainly focused on involving schools (2236), teachers (908), and students (587) in the events in order to invite them to the Community of Schools and in the initial phase of data collection. The partners' commitment also resulted in important contact with over 100 representatives of policymakers and authorities and 200 representatives of the scientific community. The general public has been involved during conferences and other events.

2.2.3 Geographical level

The partners, especially those responsible for the fieldwork, have been committed to implementing information meetings and events, especially at the local level (18 activities – 1610 people reached in total) and the national level (4 activities – 2384 people reached in total). The involvement of participants at these levels aims to create a strong base for the actual implementation of the educational practices proposed by the project.

Also, 3 events has been held at International level, attended by 235 people, and other 3 at European level with the participation of 309 people.

Detailed tables can be found in Annex 4 (tables 5 and 6).

3. Results of the dissemination activities

3.1 Knowledge

The knowledge level refers to activities that allow the main target groups to increase their understanding of LET'S CARE specific topics. The dissemination activities aimed at reaching this level of involvement represent a crucial step for the project's implementation and success. The participation of the target groups demonstrates the interest of the stakeholders in the LET'S CARE approach, and it is a promising sign for the development of the Community of Schools and Network of Stakeholders.

During dissemination events, consortium partners highlighted the central goal of LET'S CARE: to establish an educational setting that is sensitive to students' emotional and relational needs,

embraces diversity, and fosters innovation. This environment aims to enhance learning by focusing on cognitive, emotional, and social development.

In this initial stage of the project, partners conducted training and workshops centred around LET'S CARE's key principles. These sessions aimed to increase awareness among teachers and principals and provide them with basic knowledge in Safe Education, facilitating their involvement in the Community of Schools. Training topics included:

- Practical strategies for inclusive teaching.
- Pedagogical methods that prioritise learner-centered education.
- Shifting from traditional grading to narrative assessment to support children's development and well-being.
- Cooperative learning techniques.
- Foster critical thinking and personal reflection in children.
- Use art and creativity as inclusive approaches for students with intellectual disabilities and behavioural issues.

Additionally, some seminars specifically targeted headmasters and school directors, focusing on teacher well-being and school organisational aspects.

The analysis of the implementation results follows 3 main aspects:

- Dissemination Contexts (Workshops and Training events)
- Target groups (Students, Students' Families, Education Scientific Community, Teachers, Schools, Policy Makers & Authorities, European Policy Makers, NGOs & Advocacy Organisations, General Public, Others)
- Geographical level (Local, Regional, National, European, International)

3.1.1 Dissemination Contexts

Some of the partners involved in the field research have started implementing training courses, workshops, and seminars related to the general theoretical model of LET'S CARE to disseminate the approach to the target groups. These training courses have been a way to involve teachers in the Community of Schools and make them more aware of the objectives and the holistic approach that LET'S CARE is promoting. POLO has involved 4130 persons in 38 training activities. COM, JEX, and ARID have organised other training events for a total of 42 events and 4302 persons involved in total.

Detailed tables with number of training events and participants can be found in Annex 6 (tables 7 and 8).

3.1.2 Target groups

Considering the fact that the project is in its initial phase and the contents to be disseminated are still limited, the partners have achieved good results in terms of the participation of target groups. A high number of teachers (1889) have had the opportunity to improve their professionalisation through 42 training courses about the educational strategies that put the students as protagonists of their learning process in a safe environment.

Besides teachers, 140 students, 5 representatives of the education scientific community, 20 schools and 2.248 general public have participated in the training courses.

A detailed table with target groups per partner can be found in Annex 6 (table 9).

All these events have created an important starting point for the future sustainability of the project and the creation of a Community of Schools that will adopt tools and methodologies provided by the project's results and will raise awareness on the need to change the school approach by bringing greater safety to both teachers and students.

3.1.3 Geographical level

Partners have organised local in-person training courses for a total of 6 activities and 317 persons involved and 31 training activities at the national level attended by 3828 people. Then, thanks to its international network, POLO has been able to involve 157 participants from different countries, implementing 5 workshops during an international conference.

Detailed tables with number of events and participants can be found in Annex 5 (tables 10 and 11).

4. Conclusions

The analysis of the impact of the dissemination and communication activities during the first year of the project is positive. The partners have implemented communication and dissemination activities that reached schools, the scientific community, public administrations, and policymakers according to their possibilities. An excellent foundation has been laid to continue involving stakeholders and participants in future data collection and other project activities. LET'S CARE has met high interest due to its innovativeness, focus on student well-being, broad theoretical and social approach, and

potential concrete impact in the world of education as demonstrated by the number of persons involved in the dissemination activities during this first year.

The **communication** activities remarkably impacted the general public, showing the partners' commitment to sharing the project's contents and activities. In total, 4.538 participants have been involved in information activities, in detail 2.927 in conferences, 247 in information meetings and 1.364 in other events.

The **dissemination** activities have met the interest and the participation of a considerable number of target groups who have been involved in the project activities: 4.302 persons have attended the LET'S CARE-related training activities and workshops implemented by the consortium members.

Through information meetings, presentations in conferences, clustering events and training courses related to the project, the consortium has addressed all the project's target groups, reaching:

- 727 students.
- 83 students' families.
- 210 representatives of the education scientific community.
- 2.256 schools.
- 2.797 teachers and educators.
- 155 policymakers.
- 9 European policymakers.
- 27 representatives of NGOs and advocacy organisations.
- 330 general public.

During the project's second year, the LET'S CARE content addressed to teachers and other targeted groups will improve (for example, through the LET'S CARE Hub that will be launched in October), and the results of the communication and dissemination activities are expected to be largely increased.

Annex 1 – Communication Material

1 GENERAL PRESENTATION LEAFLET

Download at: <https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/s/pzwEoQDCmZcb6s4>

Image 3 – project's presentation leaflet

2 RESEARCH MODEL PRESENTATION LEAFLET

Download at: <https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/s/yZmP3s5orwQAF6F>

Image 4 – Education model validation presentation leaflet

3 GENERAL PRESENTATION OF THE PROJECT

Download at: <https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/s/yz3QLmTzABCEJ64>

Sample of the first page that the partners can adapt:

Image 5 – Presentation for the schools

4 PROJECT PRESENTATION ROLL-UP

Download at: <https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/s/Tp2sCSsj8wnjAXw>

lets care project.eu

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Let's care

BUILDING SAFE AND CARING SCHOOLS TO FOSTER EDUCATIONAL INCLUSION AND SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENT

OBJECTIVES

- Identifying **SOCIO-EMOTIONAL ROOTS** behind early school leaving and underachievement in key competences and basic skills.
- Collect data at the European level and analyse the **VARIABLES of EDUCATIONAL DISADVANTAGE** or inequality.
- Develop **EVIDENCE-BASED TOOLS** for a caring and supportive educational relationships model.
- Create a **NETWORK OF STAKEHOLDERS** for supporting policy action and enhancing social impact.
- Develop a caring **SCHOOLS COMMUNITY** at the European level.
- Advocate and propose **POLITICAL RECOMMENDATIONS** on caring schools and on combating social exclusion.

RESULTS

- SAFE EDUCATIONAL MODEL
- TEACHERS' PEER OBSERVATION COLLABORATIVE DYNAMICS
- STUDENTS' E-PORTFOLIO
- SAFE TEACHING TRAINING PROGRAM
- SAFE EDUCATION & SAFE TEACHING DATABASES
- SAFE SCHOOL LABEL

PILLARS

- Safe Education
- Safe School
- Safe Teaching
- Safe Learning

- Advocacy and policy recommendations
- School community bonding
- Teacher student relationship
- Individual student well-being

Partners: COMILLAS, ARID, PARENTS, ZABALA, CIDELIA, TIMELEX, and others.

Social media icons: Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn.

Image 6 - Roll-up of the project

5 FIRST NEWSLETTER

Available at: <https://letscaresproject.eu/newsletter-2003-1/>

Sample of the first page:

Image 7 - First page of the 1st Newsletter

6 FIRST PROMOTIONAL VIDEO

Available at: <https://tubedu.org/w/eSVAXhZFXxnz6C13QE4i2b?start=1s>

Sample screenshot:

Image 8 – Screenshot of the 1st Promotional video

7 FIRST PRESS RELEASE

LET'S CARE - Building Safe and Caring Schools to Foster Educational Inclusion and School Achievement

A European research project involving 9 European countries, 120 schools, 18000 students and 2400 teachers aimed at improving students' achievements and well-being in their educational environments. Criticalities, weaknesses and needs will be analysed to understand and improve the caring dimension of educational inclusion and school success.

LET'S CARE project, funded by the program Horizon Europe, has the ambitious goal of tackling the increasing under-achievement and early school leaving rates, by promoting the building of the **Safe School model**: a caring educational environment in an effective relational and emotional context to fosters inclusion and motivation.

From early childhood through secondary school and beyond, Let's Care aims to pinpoint the factors behind underachievement, disengagement, or dropping out of school taking into consideration four different pillars: individual, relational, community, and political. Additionally, the project advocates for innovative research to promote **safe learning, safe teaching, safe schools and safe education** by establishing **emotionally secure relationships as the foundation for teaching**. In situations of vulnerability and social disadvantage, building emotionally supportive relationships within a 'safe school' can play a crucial role in reversing these dynamics.

The implementation of the LET'S CARE project will take place over the next 3 years. The preparatory work, carried out in 9 countries (Spain, Portugal, Italy, Poland, Bulgaria, Lithuania, Austria, Belgium, Netherlands), laid the scientific foundations of the research by creating the first community of schools, carrying out preliminary theoretical and field research and developing the online hub that will gather training material, good practices and discussion space for the 2400 participating teachers. The objective is to identify the actions to be implemented to improve the relationships between teachers and pupils, school and families, local communities and politics. These actions will result in a lively and constructive environment, where all the students, even the ones from culturally and socially disadvantaged backgrounds, can express their talents, inclinations and abilities.

Students who currently experience a positive school environment and recognise their abilities and potential are likely to evolve into proactive, open-minded, and respectful citizens in the future. Essential to realising this ambitious yet vital objective is the active involvement of the broader social community connected to the school. This, indeed, is the sole indispensable factor for cultivating a healthy, democratic, inclusive, and **secure society**. LET'S CARE project will engage with over 300 stakeholders, encompassing public authorities, non-governmental and civil society organisations, teachers' and parents' associations, as well as academic institutions.

The next steps of the project will include the active participation of the schools involved in practical workshops, training courses and conferences. In each participating country, **safe teaching training courses** will be organised in-person and online, based on innovative training materials and assessment tools. **National Conferences** will then take place in each member country to disseminate the LET'S CARE model and results and to train teachers, educators and researchers in the use of the different tools. Furthermore, in 2024 the **International Teachers' Forum** will be held in Verona, where teachers from all over Europe will introduce and share the Safe Teaching practices experienced and applied in their own countries. The **final LET'S CARE International Conference** will take place in Spain in 2026 and will involve education stakeholders, decision and policy makers, together with the representatives of other European projects.

More information at: <https://letscaireproject.eu/>

Annex 2 – List of the web links with Let's care references

Web pages and media articles

<https://www.europole.org/lets-care-2/>

<https://www.ignatianum.edu.pl/horyzont-europa>

cidalia.es/lets-care/

<https://www.juntaex.es/w/educacion-proyecto-lets-care>

<https://www.educarex.es/atencion-diversidad/lets-care.html>

<https://promaestro.org/proyecto-europeo-lets-care/>

<https://promaestro.org/en/european-project-lets-care/>

<https://www.timelex.eu/en/horizon-projects/lets-care>

LET'S CARE - Construir escuelas seguras y solidarias para fomentar la inclusión educativa y el rendimiento escolar (zabala.es)

LET'S CARE - Building safe and caring schools to foster educational inclusion and school achievement (zabala.eu)

<https://parentsinternational.org/projects/>

<http://lagaceta.educarex.es/leer/consejeria-educacion-empleo-participa-proyectos-europeos-evitan-abandono-fracaso-escolar>

<https://www.europole.org/spazi-ideali-e-di-innovazione-cosa-vuol-dire-innovare-nella-scuola/>

<https://www.europole.org/corso-sulle-cause-dello-stress-degli-insegnanti/>

<https://www.europole.org/concorso-nazionale-sulla-pizza-robotica-e-inclusione/>

<https://www.europole.org/scuola-spazio-di-crescita-e-cura-nelle-relazioni-dentro-e-fuori-la-scuola/>

<https://www.europole.org/scuola-inclusiva-i-bambini-ad-alto-potenziale/>

<https://www.europole.org/corso-di-formazione-sulla-pedagogia-freinet/>

<https://www.europole.org/insegnare-la-matematica-in-modo-divertente/>

<https://www.europole.org/lezioni-di-legalita-con-alessandra-dolci/>

<https://www.europole.org/gli-insegnanti-e-il-futuro-delle-nostre-democrazie-giornata-di-studio-con-philippe-meirieu-a-verona/>

<https://prsc.lt/lt/erasmus-projektas-peec>

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2023-01-01 <https://www.prsc.lt/lt/component/events/?view=calendar>

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2023-02-01 <https://www.prsc.lt/lt/component/events/?view=calendar>

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2023-03-01 <https://www.prsc.lt/lt/component/events/?view=calendar>

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2023-04-01 <https://www.prsc.lt/lt/component/events/?view=calendar>

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2023-04-01 <https://www.prsc.lt/lt/component/events/?view=calendar>

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2023-05-01 <https://www.prsc.lt/lt/component/events/?view=calendar>

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2023-06-01 <https://www.prsc.lt/lt/component/events/?view=calendar>

https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/index.php?option=com_events&view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2023-07-01 <https://www.prsc.lt/lt/component/events/?view=calendar>

<https://prsc.lt/lt/component/events/?view=plan&tmpl=default&date=2023-08-01>

<https://www.prsc.lt/lt/component/events/?view=calendar>

<https://www.prsc.lt/lt/component/events/?view=calendar>

Social Media

<https://www.facebook.com/lacjum/posts/pfbid0GYjzRBUzKsv2Mz4X5142Ti8j5ecjBZXUuyuKjYpQpQrkz8tMiLGkDphtG4AJhxrBl>

<https://www.facebook.com/lacjum/posts/pfbid0PNQitDFMy7sm1daNdLXKsK2LCeL9Pekygr8gyYvibsXBSGGDUT49oLdT6aAvorJhl>

<https://www.facebook.com/lacjum/posts/pfbid02MMSkRw2aFhzCZ6m9CUGMj55i5b8NPFZv24YGuBr2996kA4Kjb4UXwXG4anmuuLAPI>

https://www.instagram.com/p/Cj8jkbsrBee/?img_index=1

https://www.instagram.com/p/Cn6XLA_LU4T/?img_index=1

<https://www.instagram.com/stories/highlights/18019853671624437/>

https://twitter.com/Intl_Parents/status/1583139342641295368

<https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100075494937238>

<https://www.facebook.com/prsc.lt/posts/pfbid0yRHieANhKixvzopFqPwTH4rNNVszQVGUF9ZeiF4oXJWPszGqwnSu1mZHVyHrJH5RI>

<https://www.facebook.com/prsc.lt/posts/pfbid02gGqVt4Jqrh3tYkUanvidEPYMCXWpMLFoDEcJNSErxQ2M9SvzaMxR3NvBArsuSPbl>

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/timelex_home-activity-7048612086318325760-59Xq?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

Annex 3 – Results of the communication activities - Awareness

ONLINE COMMUNICATION

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	IPA	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Media articles			159			4.672	285		55.510	196	8.220	61		60	69.163
Social media		1.841				372		135			400	700			3.448
Mailing lists						192			84.428	873	275				85.768
TOTAL		1841	159			5236	285	135	139947	1069	8895	761		60	158388

Table 1 – Online Communication (views)

Graph 1 – Online communication (views)

Annex 4 – Results of the communication activities - Information

NUMBER OF EVENTS PER CONTEXTS OF DISSEMINATION

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FH V	IPA	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Conferences		2		5	1				1				1		10
Information meetings	2	1						3	1		1		3		11
Events		2		1				1	2						6
Clustering activities				1											1
TOTAL	2	5		7	1			4	4		1		4		28

Table 2 – Number of events per context of dissemination

Graph 2 – Number of events per context of dissemination

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS PER CONTEXTS OF DISSEMINATION

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	IPA	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Conferences		520		2.157	15				170				65		2.927
Information meetings	82	45						51	31		30		8		247
Events		435		291				181	433						1.340
Clustering activities				24											24
TOTAL	82	1.000		2.472	15			232	634		30		73		4.538

Table 3 - Number of participants / audience per context of dissemination's event and per partner

Graph 3 - Number of participants / audience per context of dissemination's event and per partner

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS PER CONTEXTS OF DISSEMINATION

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	IPA	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Students				30	15			158	378				6		587
Families								30	49				4		83
Education Scientific Community		110		84				7					4		205
Teachers	76	600						17	140		25		50		908
Schools	2	155		2.065				3			3		8		2.236
Policy Makers & Authorities	4	120						8	20		2		1		155
European Policy Makers									5						5
NGOs & Advocacy Organisations		15		2					10						27
General Public				291				9	30						330
Others									2						2
TOTAL	82	1.000		2.472	15			232	634		30		73		4.538

Table 4 - Number of participants / audience per target group and per partner

Graph 4 - Number of participants / audience per target group and per partner

NUMBER AND GEOGRAPHICAL KINDS OF DISSEMINATION EVENTS (CONFERENCES, INFO MEETINGS, EVENTS, CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES)

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	IPA	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
International				1	1				1						3
European		1		2											3
National				2					2						4
Regional / Local	2	4		2				4	1		1		4		18
TOTAL	2	5		7	1			4	4		1		4		28

Table 5 - Number and Geographical kinds of Dissemination Events

Graph 5 - Number and Geographical kinds of Dissemination Events

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS PER GEOGRAPHICAL DISSEMINATION EVENT AND PER PARTNER

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	IPA	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
International				50	15				170						235
European		220		89											309
National				2.291					93						2.384
Regional / Local	82	780		42				232	371		30		73		1.610
TOTAL		1.000		2.472	15			232	634		30		73		4.538

Table 6 - Number of participants / audience per geographical dissemination event and per partner

Graph 6 - Number of participants/audience per geographical dissemination event and per partner

Annex 5 – Participation to conferences

APRENDER SEGUROS: ESCUELAS QUE CUIDAN (ASEC)

SAFE LEARNING: CARING SCHOOLS

Partner: COMILLAS

Place: Madrid (Spain)

Date: 4/11/2022

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

Second session (3h) of Module 1 (Promoting safety in the classroom) of the training program “Aprender Seguros: Escuelas que Cuidan (ASEC) -Safe Learning: Caring schools”. ASEC objectives are to sensitise and train teachers to detect, understand and manage the affective needs of children at school, to assist in the establishment of good care partnerships with families, and to integrate a model of care and intervention focused on the security of relationships into the coordination/management teams. This is a 19hs training, and it is made up of 3 modules (9, 6 and 4 hours, respectively).

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

Colloquium, sensitisation on the importance of attachment in the school environment and its repercussions. Knowledge about the development of the LET’S CARE project, its connection with the course and its usefulness.

OUTCOME(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

Networking contacts and interest of the school community.

EVIDENCE

<https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/s/WWArzSz2oKDxgYi>

PEACE AS EDUCATIONAL VALUE – A SCHOOL WITHOUT CONFLICTS

Partner: POLO

Place: Verona (Italy)

Date: 3/12/2022

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

The international conference “Peace as educational value - A school without conflicts” has been organised by POLO in Verona to gather outstanding speakers from different countries around the world, whose valuable experiences and contributions provided a clear picture of how schools can become an ideal growth environment for a more equitable future society. The conference has been entirely dedicated to education, solidarity and democracy with the aim of promoting a peaceful model of society, characterised primarily by respect for diversity. The audience present (from 10 different European countries and from India) was highly diverse: teachers, educators, trainers and school managers, but also university students, representatives of civil society organisations and NGOs, policy makers. This diversity further enriched the dialogue and sharing of perspectives during the event. The LET’S CARE project was presented during the conference as its goals and objectives are in perfect harmony with the values promoted during the event. Furthermore, five dedicated workshops were held, each addressing specific topics related to the LET’S CARE project.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBPAGE

<https://www.europole.org/conference2022/> <https://www.europole.org/conferenza2022/>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

The objectives and values on which the Let’s Care project is based were presented to the participants.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

Participants in the conference gave very positive feedback and expressed their interest in following the project’s progress. On this occasion, POLO has collected requests from schools to join the LET’S CARE Community of Schools and from teachers who expressed interest and willingness to participate in future project activities.

EVIDENCE

<https://www.europole.org/conference2022/> (the collected signatures cannot be publicly shared)

FINDING THE ROOTS OF HOPE

Partner: Comillas (Berástegui, A) Place: Manresa (Spain)

Date: 17/01/2023

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

The conference titled “Finding the roots of hope”, has been developed within the framework of the Pastoral Conference Manresa 2023 which gathers management teams from of the European network of JECSE schools. The conference is related to the project because it focuses on hope, safe learning and child and adolescent’s mental health in Europe.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE

<https://jecse.org/2023/01/22/709/>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

<p>How to strengthen hope?</p>	
<p>Designing the ways</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generate alternative routes and paths, evaluation and change Stop! Stop! Small big goals into smaller ones Start with the first step and build in some early success Anticipate possible obstacles and prepare review we all you would do something Keep asking alternative options to your repetition Be aware of your own resources Build in and give in the support you need (supportive external agents) family, peers, mentors Use failure to learn Be able to adjust and re-evaluate goals 	

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

The conference has been an occasion for networking and planning new conferences for School Principals.

EVIDENCE:

<https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/s/xQZ4rp95RHQz2wH>

WHO EDUCATES?: NON-FORMAL EDUCATION AND THE FAMILY

EDUCATION AND THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

Partner: **Comillas** Place: **Santiago de Compostela (Spain)** Date: **18/02/2023**

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

Comillas has participated in the symposium entitled “Who educates?: non-formal education and the family” at the World Conference on Education: “Education and the Sustainable Development Goals” held in Santiago de Compostela on February 16-18, 2023. The presentation of the project during the conference contributed to the improvement of education by highlighting the importance of family ties in the development of safe learning.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

<https://ciec.edu.co/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/programa-conferencia-mundial.pdf>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

Comillas has presented objectives, aims and progression of the LET’S CARE project.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

The presentation of the project reached the interest of the scientific community, and it has been a positive occasion for networking and new contacts.

EVIDENCE

<https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/s/z52zeGZAL39GSYM>

CRISIS INTERVENTION – CHALLENGES

Partner: ARID

Place: Dobczyce (Poland)

Date: 09/03/2023

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

The conference was devoted to crisis intervention topics, which are partially relevant to Let's Care project because topics discussed during the conference were addressing children's problems and school problems as well. Moreover, the conference was organised in the blended learning formula, so we have participants from all over Poland. Those were educators, teachers, directors of schools and crisis intervention centers' staff.

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

ARID presented the aims and the objective of the project, introducing future research activities.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

Some schools have declared preliminary willingness to take part in the project activities. Also, teachers asked about the details of the project and its results.

ANNUAL PhD MEETING. JORNADA DE DOCTORANDOS DEL PROGRAM INDIVIDUO, FAMILIA, Y SOCIEDAD: UNA VISIÓN MULTIDISCIPLINAR

Partner: Comillas

Place: Madrid (Spain)

Date: 21/04/2023

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE:

This annual PhD meeting is a space made available to PhD candidates at Comillas University to reflect on the social impact of the various research areas that exist in the Program. Its main aim is creating synergies and fostering encounters among emerging researchers. Three members of the COM team participated in an annual PhD meeting to introduce an overview of the LET'S CARE EE project to a university audience of mostly emerging researchers.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article):

<https://eventos.comillas.edu/96368/detail/jornada-de-doctorandos-del-programa-individuo-familia-y-sociedad-del-2023.html>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE:

LET'S CARE team members Giulia Di Lisio, Alba Couso, and Antonio Milá presented an overview of the Let's Care project to an audience comprised of mostly emerging researchers from the Social Sciences "Individuo, Familia, y Sociedad" PhD programme. Preliminary results of the T2.1 systematic literature review were also presented.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION:

Our main results included dissemination of the University's involvement as Project Coordinators of LET'S CARE, as well as networking with interested researchers who provided feedback about the relevance of the project and its theoretical and methodological connection with other research projects the university is involved in.

EVIDENCE

<https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/s/gE6tXp4jHTF3Qz8>

<https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/s/77DBmgmFzXCZBrA>

FÓRUM EDUCAÇÃO E INOVAÇÃO

Partner: UCP

Place: Porto (Portugal)

Date: **27/04/2023**

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

This Forum was organised by Colégio Nossa Senhora do Rosário, a private school in Porto, Portugal. The target groups of this event were the school community of this school (teachers, non-teaching staff, parents) and partners. This event had a regional impact (Porto Metropolitan Area). LET'S CARE project was presented by Lurdes Veríssimo at a round-table focused on "School as a context of relation".

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE

<https://www.colegiodorosario.pt/newsDetail.aspx?newsID=536>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

The rationale of the project was presented and how it positively can contribute to improving relations in the school context.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

The participation at this event was relevant to strengthening the interest of this school in being part of the Community of Schools of LET'S CARE and to share some reflections and practical implications of the key ideas of the project for pedagogical practice.

EVIDENCE:

https://www.colegiodorosario.pt/ForumEducacaoInovacao/Programa_FEI.pdf

<https://cloud.europole.org/index.php/s/ZQGY2wMb3Kc9iNf>

OUT OF THE NET – FINAL CONFERENCE

Partner: ARID

Place: Sofia (Bulgaria)

Date: 02/06/2023

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

The conference was devoted to school education, especially for the Hikikomori syndrome prevention. The conference has been organised in the framework of the Erasmus+ project “Out of The Net” by KITE and involved a hundred teachers, experts in the educational field and university professors.

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

A representative of ARID has described the project aims and expected results.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION *(e.g. interest of the scientific community, networking contacts, new stakeholders involved, etc.)*

Since the conference was organised by KITE, this transnational synergy supported the partner to engage more teachers. After the conference teachers and university professors looked for further information about how to be part of the project.

ICE/IEEE: SHAPING THE FUTURE

DATA-DRIVEN ENGINEERING, INNOVATION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Partner: FHV

Place: Edinburgh (UK)

Date: 19-22/06/2023

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

ICE IEEE/ITMC is the International Conference on Engineering, Technology, and Innovation, part of the IEEE Technology and Engineering Management Society (TEMS). The ICE conference discusses systems engineering as a socio-technical task focusing on the design of products and services, and the entrepreneurial innovation process for its adoption in society and the economy. In line with Edinburgh's strategic vision, the ICE 2023 Conference had a specific focus on data-driven engineering, innovation and entrepreneurship.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE

<https://blogs.ed.ac.uk/ice-2023/>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

Within this scholarly article, FHV presented LET'S CARE approach to fostering students' attachment security. At the centre is the design and development of a tailored service system, a Content Management System that addresses the relational attachment of students to their teachers. Based on the contextual environment (the Attachment Theory) and the theoretical underpinning (Service Science), FHV presented how the project applies the research method of Design Science Research to analyse and evaluate as well as to recommend a CMS for this purpose. In doing so, two analyses have been performed: a framework-based analysis and a Service Science related analysis.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

Recommendation of the Let's Care Hub's IT infrastructure.

EVIDENCE

Publication available at:

https://journals.scholarsportal.info/details/26938855/v2023inone/1_dadoasacmsba.xml

Computer Science Bibliography: <https://dblp.org/db/conf/ice-itmc/ice-itmc2023.html>

ENCUENTRO QUE TRANSFORMA: CUIDADO Y ESCUCHA EN LA ESCUELA COLLOQUIUM "LISTENING AND CARING"

Partner: Comillas

Place: Granada (Sapin)

Date: 25/11/2023

SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE CONFERENCE

The colloquium "Listening and caring" has been presented at the Congress of Catholic Schools: inspiring meetings held in Granada on November 24-26, 2022 and organised by the Federation of Catholic Schools of Spain with the aim of highlighting the dimension of care in the education system and where the LET'S CARE project aims were presented.

LINK TO THE CONFERENCE WEBSITE (or page, or blog article)

<https://inspiradoresdeencuentros.esuelascaticas.es/>

PROJECT RESULT(S) OR CONTENT(S) THAT HAS BEEN PRESENTED IN THE CONFERENCE

During the colloquium prof Berastegui presented the main values, aims and objectives of LET'S CARE.

RESULT(S) REACHED WITH THE PARTICIPATION

The Congress has been an important occasion for networking

EVIDENCE

<https://inspiradoresdeencuentros.esuelascaticas.es/speaker/ana-berastegui/>

Annex 6 – Results of the dissemination activities - Knowledge

NUMBER OF EVENTS PER CONTEXT OF IMPLEMENTATION

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	IPA	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Training events		1		2			1		38						42
TOTAL		1		2			1		38						42

Table 7 - Number of events per context of implementation

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS PER CONTEXT OF IMPLEMENTATION

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	IPA	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Training events		125		24			23		4.130						4.302
TOTAL		125		24			23		4.130						4.302

Table 8 - Number of participants per context of implementation and per partner

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS PER TARGET GROUP AND PER PARTNER

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	IPA	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Students		20							120						140
Education Scientific Community		5													5
Teachers		80		24			23		1.762						1.889
Schools		20													20
General Public									2.248						2.248
TOTAL		125		24			23		4.130						4.302

Table 9 - Number of participants per context of implementation and per partner

Graph 7 - Number of participants per context of implementation and per partner

NUMBER AND GEOGRAPHICAL KINDS OF DISSEMINATION EVENTS (EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING EVENTS)

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	IPA	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
Inter-national									5						5
National									31						31
Regional / Local		1		2			1		2						6
TOTAL		1		2			1		38						42

Table 10 - Number and Geographical kinds of Dissemination Events

Graph 8 - Number and Geographical kinds of Dissemination Events

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS / AUDIENCE PER GEOGRAPHICAL DISSEMINATION EVENT AND PER PARTNER

	AIK	ARID	CID	COM	FHV	IPA	JEX	KITE	POLO	PROMA	PRSC	TLX	UPC	ZIC	TOTAL
International									157						157
National									3.828						3.828
Regional / Local		125		24			23		145						317
TOTAL		125		24			23		4.130						4.302

Table 11 - Number of participants / audience per geographical dissemination event and per partner

Graph 9 - Number of participants / audience per geographical dissemination event and per partner